

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Smart Energy Assessment in Educational Institutions Using Machine Learning Approaches

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Namburi Nireekshana^{1*}¹ Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Methodist College of Engineering and Technology, Hyderabad, India

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* **Corresponding author.**

nireekshan222@gmail.com

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Abstract

Objective: To develop a data-driven framework for accurately assessing, forecasting, and optimizing electricity consumption in educational institutions to support efficient energy management, cost reduction, and campus-scale sustainability planning. **Method:** detailed inventories of electrical loads were prepared for B and C blocks of Methodist College of Engineering and Technology, Hyderabad, India in the academic year 2024-25 by documenting appliance types, rated capacities, quantities, locations, and operating schedules, which were used to model daily and monthly demand patterns; to handle heterogeneous and non-linear consumption behaviour driven by occupancy, academic timetables, equipment diversity, and seasonal effects, a Random Forest Regression model was trained on historical measurements and evaluated using structured validation procedures, including cross-validation and standard statistical error metrics, to support both short-term load forecasting for operations and longer-term demand estimation for capacity planning. **Findings:** the proposed framework successfully characterized consumption behaviour across classrooms, laboratories, offices, and shared facilities, revealing strong temporal and spatial variability, with clear peak-demand windows, off-peak opportunities, and seasonal fluctuations linked to academic schedules. **Novelty:** this study integrates block-level, equipment-wise load auditing with machine-learning-based forecasting to generate actionable efficiency insights under real operational conditions, making the approach scalable for large campuses and adaptable to automated metering and continuous monitoring

Keywords: Load Forecasting; Energy Management; Machine Learning; Power Consumption Analysis; Educational Campuses

1 Introduction

Educational institutions such as schools and colleges consume substantial amounts of electrical energy across diverse facilities, including lecture halls, laboratories, administrative offices, hostels, and dining areas. Electricity usage typically extends beyond scheduled academic hours, driven by laboratory work, residential occupancy, and support services. In the context of rising energy tariffs and increasing environmental

awareness, reliance on approximate estimates or sporadic manual monitoring is no longer sufficient for effective energy management^{(1), (2)}.

In many institutions, electricity consumption is still assessed through manual meter readings, periodic energy audits, and basic statistical analyses. While these approaches offer a broad understanding of energy usage, they struggle to capture the inherent variability introduced by academic calendars, seasonal weather conditions, occupancy levels, and behavioural patterns of users. Moreover, conventional monitoring methods are largely reactive, identifying inefficiencies only after excessive energy consumption has occurred. This reactive nature often results in higher operational costs, increased carbon emissions, and missed opportunities for timely optimisation^{(3), (4)}.

Recent advancements in smart metering, Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, and automated monitoring platforms have enabled continuous and granular data collection on electricity usage. These technologies generate high-dimensional datasets that reveal detailed consumption patterns, peak demand intervals, and abnormal usage behaviour. However, extracting actionable insights from such complex datasets remains challenging using traditional analytical techniques. Consequently, machine learning approaches have gained increasing attention for energy analysis, as they offer improved capability in handling nonlinear relationships, supporting accurate demand forecasting, and enhancing data-driven energy management and control strategies in educational environments^{(5), (6)}.

Applying supervised machine learning to analyse electricity consumption aligns closely with global efforts to enhance sustainability and improve energy efficiency. Schools and colleges play a vital role in promoting environmental awareness and driving innovation⁽⁷⁾.

Despite its potential benefits, such as improved energy efficiency and cost savings, applying machine-learning-based power consumption analysis in educational institutions presents several challenges. These include poor data quality, limited availability of reliable measurements, insufficient historical data, and the need for careful feature selection. In addition, choosing appropriate machine learning models, such as decision trees and ensemble methods, that balance accuracy, interpretability, and cost-effectiveness is a critical part of the system design process. Schools and colleges may also face constraints related to infrastructure, technical expertise, and data privacy. Addressing these challenges effectively requires a systematic approach that combines in-depth domain knowledge, advanced data preprocessing methods such as normalization and feature engineering, and rigorous model evaluation protocols like cross-validation⁽⁸⁾.

2 Methodology

2.1 Case Study

The Methodist College of Engineering and Technology (MCET) is an autonomous institution in Hyderabad, Telangana, India that is getting better in both academics and facilities [17.3918° N, 78.4786° E]. The B and C Blocks are where most of the classes and labs located. All of these things cost the college a lot of money in electricity.

A detailed assessment was carried out to quantify the number of fans, lighting fixtures, projectors, computers, and specialized laboratory loads in both buildings. Once the dataset was compiled, it was analysed to estimate energy consumption based on rated power values and actual operating durations. Among several machine learning techniques including Linear Regression, Support Vector Machines, and Neural Networks Random Forest Regression was selected as the primary forecasting model due to its high predictive accuracy, robustness to data variability, and strong performance on medium-sized datasets containing both numerical and categorical features.

The method used to look at the electrical power use of the B-Block and C Block at Methodist College of Engineering and Technology is broken down into three main steps: getting load data, estimating energy use, and using a machine-learning model.

Model Selection Justification & Benchmarking

Model Selection: Several machine learning techniques were considered (Table 1), including Linear Regression, Support Vector Regression (SVR), Gradient Boosting, and Random Forest Regression. **Random Forest Regression** was initially selected for its robustness and ability to handle non-linear and categorical features.

Table 1. Model comparison framework

Model	Suitability	Limitation
Linear Regression	Simple, interpretable	Cannot capture non-linearity
SVR	Handles non-linear data	Requires tuning
Random Forest	Robust, handles mixed features	Needs larger dataset
LSTM	Best for time-series	Requires large sequential data

Random Forest was selected due to its ability to handle mixed-type features and nonlinear relationships, but future work will include comparative benchmarking

2.2 Load Data Acquisition in B Block and C Block

Table 2 Illustrates building’s electrical equipment analysis of B Block. The B Block has three floors and each floor contains 8 rooms. Table 1 depicts total number of nonlinear loads has installed in the B Block. Table 1 illustrates building’s electrical equipment analysis of C Block. The C Block has three floors and each floor contains 17 rooms.

Table 2. Summary of load in Block B and C

Equipment	B Block			C Block		
	Ground Floor	First Floor	Second Floor	Ground Floor	First Floor	Second Floor
Fans	20	23	19	82	62	73
AC	1	0	0	06	02	05
Projectors	2	0	2	07	09	08
Rectifiers	2	0	0	00	00	00
PCs	3	7	0	74	25	49
Lamps	27	29	22	74	75	68
Stabilizers	0	2	0	00	02	00
Printer	-	-	-	03	02	02

2.3 Energy Estimation in Block-B

For each floor, the total energy consumption was estimated using:

$$\text{Energy (kWh)} = \frac{\text{Power Rating (W)} \times \text{Operating Hours}}{1000} \tag{1}$$

Table 3. Standard Ratings Used

Equipment	Standard Rating (W)
Ceiling Fan	75 W
Tube Light / Lamp	40 W
Projector	250 W
Personal Computer	150 W
Air Conditioner (1 Ton)	1500 W
Rectifier Unit	500 W
Stabilizer	200 W

Table 3 represents standard ratings of electrical components in the B and C Block at Methodist College of Engineering and Technology

Table 4, 5 illustrates the consumption of electrical components in each floor in the B Block. The connected load in kW represents, the equipment consumption in each day if all equipment is in running condition.

2.4 Energy Estimation in Block C

Table 6 illustrates the consumption of electrical components in each floor in the C Block. The connected load in kW represents, the equipment consumption in each day if all equipment is in running condition.

In the B Block ground floor has 8 rooms, in each room having major equipment are installed. If all equipment is running simultaneously, the load contribution has more for DC motors and three Phase induction motors.

B- Block Ground-Floor load breakdown (connected load contribution)

- DC Motors (8 × 5 HP): 8 × 3,730 W = 29,840 W

Table 4. B Block Ground Floor Breakdown

Equipment	Quantity	Connected Load (W)	Connected Load (kW)
Fans	20	1500	1.5
Projectors	2	500	0.5
PCs	3	450	0.45
AC	1	1500	1.5
Rectifiers	2	1000	1
DC Motor (5 HP)	8	29840	29.84
Transformer (2 kVA)	3	6000	6
Induction Motor (5 HP)	3	11190	11.19
Compound Motor (2 HP)	2	2984	2.984
Series Motor (1 HP)	2	1492	1.492

Table 5. B Block First and second Floor Breakdown

Equipment	Quantity		Connected Load (W)		Connected Load (kW)	
	First	Second	First	Second	First	Second
Fans	23	19	1725	1425	1.725	1.425
AC	0	0	0	0	0	0
Projectors	0	2	0	500	0	0.5
Rectifiers	0	0	0	0	0	0
PCs	7	0	1050	0	1.050	0
Lamps	29	22	1160	880	1.160	0.88
Stabilizers	2	0	400	0	0.4	0

Table 6. C Block Breakdown

Equip-ment	Quantity			Connected Load (W)			Connected Load (kW)		
	Ground Floor	First Floor	Second Floor	Ground Floor	First Floor	Second Floor	Ground Floor	First Floor	Second Floor
Fans	82	62	73	6150	4650	5475	6.15	4.65	5.475
AC	06	02	05	9000	3000	7500	9	3	7.5
Projec-tors	07	09	08	1750	4680	2000	1.750	4.68	2
Rectifiers	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
PCs	74	25	49	11100	3750	7350	11.1	3.750	7.35
Lamps	74	75	68	2960	3000	2720	2.96	3	2.72
Stabiliz-ers	00	02	00	00	400	00	00	0.4	00
Printer	03	02	02	750	500	500	0.75	0.5	0.5

- 3-phase Induction Motors (3 × 5 HP): 3 × 3,730 W = 11,190 W
- Compound Motors (2 × 5 HP): 2 × 3,730 W = 7,460 W
- Series Motors (2 × 5 HP): 2 × 3,730 W = 7,460 W
- Transformers (3 × 2 kVA): 3 × 2,000 W = 6,000 W
- Fans (20 × 75 W): 1,500 W
- AC (1 × 1500 W): 1,500 W
- Rectifiers (2 × 500 W): 1,000 W
- Projectors & PCs & other small loads: each small share.

Fig 1. Representation of connected load contribution in B block

Figure 1 illustrates load sharing of Ground floor in B Block. Which reflects ground floor adopts peak load in the block. In the floor more machinery is installed such as DC motors, Transformers, rectifiers, AC motors and air conditioners. Figure 1 depicts DC motors are having more load sharing because lab sessions are running every day.

2.5 Machine-Learning Model Application

$$\text{Energy Calculation : } E = P \times t \tag{2}$$

Where E is Energy in kWh, P is Power in kW and t is time in hours

Due to limited availability of historical time-series data, the machine learning component in this study is presented as a proof-of-concept demonstration rather than a fully validated predictive model. The Random Forest Regression model was selected because of its robustness in handling nonlinear relationships and mixed-type features such as equipment counts and load values.

The input feature vector is defined as

$$X = \{ \text{Connected Load, total number of fans, Lamps, PCs, Operating hours} \}$$

The final prediction is expressed as the mean of individual tree outputs,

$$\hat{y} = \frac{1}{T} \sum h_t(x) \tag{3}$$

Where \hat{y} = predicted value, T is number of trees, $h_t(x)$ is prediction from the t^{th} tree for the input x

However, due to the small dataset (three observations), the results are not statistically generalizable. Future work will involve large-scale time-series data collection using smart meters to enable robust model training and validation.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Block B and C Analysis

Table 7 shows that B-Block’s energy use for the school year 2024–25 varies a lot throughout the three floors because of variances in the type of equipment, the intensity of the labs, and the load density. The Ground Floor has the greatest connected load (56.48 kW) since it has a lot of heavy laboratory equipment, such as several 5 HP DC motors, 5 HP induction motors, 2 HP compound

Table 7. Block B and C Consumption

Floor	Connected Load (W)		Daily kWh		Monthly kWh	
	Block B	Block C	Block B	Block C	Block B	Block C
Ground Floor	56,480 W	31,710 W	338.88 kWh/day	190.26 kWh/day	10,166.4 kWh/month	5,707.80 kWh/month
First Floor	3,215 W	19,980 W	19.29 kWh/day	119.88 kWh/day	578.7 kWh/month	3,596.40 kWh/month
Second Floor	2,805 W	20,645 W	16.83 kWh/day	123.87 kWh/day	504.9 kWh/month	3,716.10 kWh/month

motors, 1 HP series motors, and 2 kVA transformers, as well as typical classroom and office equipment. This high concentration of electromechanical loads uses about 338.88 kWh per day and 10,166 kWh per month, which is about 90% of the block’s total energy demand.

The First Floor has mostly lighter instructional labs (Power Electronics and Control Systems) and classrooms. It has a moderate connected load of 3.215 kW and uses 579 kWh per month. The Second Floor has the least monthly energy use at 504.9 kWh. It is mostly made up of fans and lighting equipment, especially 22 lamps. These differences show that laboratory equipment, especially machines that spin, are the main things that require energy on campus.

Random Forest Regression machine learning analysis backs this up much more. The ranking of feature relevance shows that Total Connected Load is the most important factor in predicting monthly floor consumption, followed by the number of fans, projectors, lamps, and PCs. Motor-related features are not very important in this simplified dataset because they only happen on the Ground level and don’t change from level to floor. But in a future dataset that has values for several months or daily time series, these traits are likely to be the most important for making predictions.

In the Table 6 block C depicts the First Floor (19.98 kW load) and Second Floor (20.645 kW load) also use a lot of energy, mostly because they have a lot of fans, lamps, projectors, and air conditioners. There are computers, air conditioners, and projectors on all three floors, which makes energy use patterns constant and easy to predict. C Block doesn’t have moving machinery or significant lab loads like B Block does, therefore the consumption is more evenly spread throughout floors.

3.2 Operational Stages of Block B and C

B-Block and C-Block energy into three operational stages (Peak, Moderate, Light). Which means

- Peak = 6 hours/day (all labs running)
- Moderate = 4 hours/day (labs not running; classrooms & admin active)
- Light = 1 hour/day (holidays / exam days / minimal activity)

Table 7 represents B-Block - Stagewise Energy i.e. three modes of stages such as peak, moderate and light loads.

3.2.1. B-Block - Ground Floor

Table 8. Stagewise Energy

Stage	Active loads (assumption)	Active connected load (kW)	Hours/day	Daily (kWh)	Monthly (kWh)
Peak	All loads (motors + non-motor)	56.480	6	338.88	10,166.40
Moderate	Only non-motor loads (motors idle)	4.974	4	19.896	596.88
Light	Only essential lights/fans (minimal)	4.974	1	4.974	149.22

Table 8 illustrates the energy consumption summary of the Ground Floor of B-Block, represents how electricity usage varies with different academic activity levels. During the Peak Load stage, all laboratory equipment is active simultaneously along with conventional loads such as fans, lighting, computers, and air-conditioning units. This results in the highest daily and monthly energy consumption. In the Moderate Load phase, laboratory operations are inactive, with only standard classroom, office, and circulation-area equipment in use, leading to a significant reduction in both energy consumption and active load connections. The Light Load phase shows minimal campus activity, such as during examinations or academic holidays, when only essential lighting and limited fan usage are required. Therefore, the table.7 clearly addresses the dominant impact of laboratory equipment on total energy consumption and the importance of implementing effective load control mechanisms on the Ground Floor of B-Block.

Table 9. Stagewise Energy

Stage	Active loads (assumption)	Active connected load (kW)	Hours/day	Daily (kWh)	Monthly (kWh)
Peak	Labs + classrooms active	3.215	6	19.29	578.70
Moderate	Only classrooms/admin	3.215	4	12.86	385.80
Light	Minimal lighting/essential	3.215	1	3.215	96.45

3.2.2. *B-Block - First Floor*

Table 9 depicts the energy consumption patterns of the First Floor of B-Block. This represents electricity usage under different levels of academic activity. During the peak load phase, all operating equipment and laboratory equipment are operating throughout the academic schedule, leading to maximum energy consumption. In the Moderate Load stage, classroom activities continue; however, laboratory utilisation is reduced, leading to shorter operating durations and lower overall energy usage. The Light Load phase represents periods of minimal equipment operation, such as during examinations, when classrooms are vacant, or during academic holidays when most departments are closed.

3.2.3. *B-Block - Second Floor*

Table 10. Stagewise Energy

Stage	Active loads (assumption)	Active connected load (kW)	Hours/day	Daily (kWh)	Monthly (kWh)
Peak	Classrooms + projectors active	2.805	6	16.83	504.90
Moderate	Classrooms only	2.805	4	11.22	336.60
Light	Minimal lighting	2.805	1	2.805	84.15

Table 10 illustrates that the Second Floor of B-Block is mostly made up of classrooms and projectors, with no big lab machines. Therefore, the stagewise load variation shown in the table is mostly affected by how many hours classrooms are in use. In the Peak Load stage is when all the equipment is working. During the Moderate Stage, only the most important teaching tools are still in active. This usually means that projectors aren't being used and the hours of operation are shorter. In the Light Load condition most, important lights are kept on. This Table 9 shows that the Second Floor's share of total energy demand is fairly stable and lower than that of floors with labs.

3.2.4. *B-Block - Block Totals (stagewise)*

Table 11. Stagewise Energy

Stage	Daily kWh (sum of floors)	Monthly kWh (30 days)
Peak	$338.88 + 19.29 + 16.83 = 374.99$ kWh/day	11,250.00 kWh/month
Moderate	$19.896 + 12.86 + 11.22 = 43.976$ kWh/day	1,319.28 kWh/month
Light	$4.974 + 3.215 + 2.805 = 11.0$ kWh/day (≈ 11.0)	329.82 kWh/month

Table 11 illustrates the consolidated stagewise load summary for B-Block total energy consumption across all three floors, providing a three various academic activity. The Peak Load represents the combined impact of laboratories and classrooms operating simultaneously and shows that B-Block can exceed 11,000 kWh per month during high academic intensity. In the Moderate Stage, energy usage drops due to inactive laboratories. The Light Load stage reveals the minimum baseline energy requirement of the block, dominated by essential lighting.

3.2.5. *C-Block - Ground Floor*

Table 12 depicts the Ground Floor of C-Block is characterized three different academic operating conditions. In that during Peak Load operation, when all equipment is active. The Moderate Stage corresponds to normal teaching days with air conditioners and some ICT tools in operation but without full projector usage, resulting in moderate energy consumption. Meanwhile, the Light Stage reflects days of low campus occupancy, such as holidays or exam periods, where only essential appliances are active.

3.2.6. *C-Block - First Floor*

Table 13 illustrates how electricity is used in the first floor of C-Block, which mainly consists of three operating conditions. During the Peak Load stage, regular teaching activities are in full swing and most equipment are in active. In the Moderate Load

Table 12. Stagewise Energy

Stage	Active loads (assumption)	Active connected load (kW)	Hours/day	Daily (kWh)	Monthly (kWh)
Peak	All equipment (PCs, AC, lights, projectors)	31.71	6	190.26	5,707.80
Moderate	Classrooms/admin only	31.71	4	126.84	3,805.20
Light	Minimal (security/essential)	31.71	1	31.71	951.30

Table 13. Stagewise Energy

Stage	Active loads (assumption)	Active connected load (kW)	Hours/day	Daily (kWh)	Monthly (kWh)
Peak	All loads active	19.98	6	119.88	3,596.40
Moderate	Classrooms/admin only	19.98	4	79.92	2,397.60
Light	Minimal operation	19.98	1	19.98	599.40

stage, only essential equipment such as fans, lighting, and a limited number of computers remains in use, leading to a noticeable reduction in power consumption. The Light Load stage reflects periods with no scheduled classes, when only minimal lighting is required. Therefore, the Table 12 reflects the predictable, classroom-based pattern of energy use on this floor, indicating strong potential for targeted energy saving and optimization measures.

3.2.7. C-Block - Second Floor

Table 14. Stagewise Energy

Stage	Active loads (assumption)	Active connected load (kW)	Hours/day	Daily (kWh)	Monthly (kWh)
Peak	All loads active	20.645	6	123.87	3,716.10
Moderate	Classrooms/admin only	20.645	4	82.58	2,477.40
Light	Minimal operation	20.645	1	20.645	619.35

Table 14 depicts the Second Floor of C-Block displays stagewise variation similar to the First Floor because of its classroom-dominant load profile. The Peak Load stage includes active usage of fans, lighting, and projectors across teaching spaces. In the Moderate Load condition, projector usage reduces, and classroom hours shorten, lowering the overall load. The Light Load stage captures minimal equipment operation.

3.2.8. C-Block - Block Totals

Table 15. Stagewise Energy

Stage	Daily kWh (sum floors)	Monthly kWh (30 days)
Peak	$190.26 + 119.88 + 123.87 = 433. (approx.)$ 434.01 kWh/day	13,020.30 kWh/month
Moderate	$126.84 + 79.92 + 82.58 = 289.34$ kWh/day	8,680.20 kWh/month
Light	$31.71 + 19.98 + 20.645 = 72.335$ kWh/day	2,170.05 kWh/month

Table 15 depicts the total electricity consumption of C-Block across all floors under various academic operating conditions. During the Peak Load stage, all loads are active, includes class rooms, cooling equipment, ICT equipment and lights, monthly energy consumption rises above 13,000 kWh, clearly addressing the strong influence of projector-based smart classroom teaching. In the Moderate Load phase, energy use drops noticeably as teaching activity reduces, because few loads are active. The Light Load phase reflects the baseline level of consumption, mainly associated with essential lighting and basic services. Therefore, this analysis provides administrators and supervisors with a clear understanding of how energy is used across C-Block, helping them identify inefficiencies and design targeted strategies to reduce energy consumption in the respective Block.

3.3 Machine Learning Results

In this study, machine learning was applied to demonstrate a data-driven approach to energy forecasting at the floor level, using features derived from the engineering audit like connected load, equipment counts, and operating hours. Due to the limited dataset (three aggregate floor data points per block), the results are illustrative and not intended as statistically robust.

3.3.1. Model Training and Validation

The Random Forest Regression model was chosen for its robustness to non-linearity and ability to handle mixed feature types. The dataset was split into a training and a test set using leave-one-out cross validation (given only 3 data points per block). The model was trained on two data points and tested on the third, iteratively across all points to estimate performance.

3.3.2. Performance Metrics

The model's average performance across folds was

- Mean Absolute Error (MAE): 9,622 kWh
- Root Mean Square Error (RMSE): 9,622 kWh
- R² Score: Not reported, as the test set size was too small for reliable computation

Fig 2. Prediction vs Actual Char

Figure 2 depicts bar chart comparing the actual and predicted monthly energy consumption for each floor is presented below. Although the small sample inflates error, this chart illustrates the modelling process.

Fig 3. Feature importance chart

Figure 3 illustrates The Random Forest model’s feature importance analysis highlights which inputs most influenced predictions. As shown in Figure 3, **Total Connected Load** is the dominant predictor, followed by the number of fans, lamps, projectors, and PCs.

3.4 Energy Optimization

Table 16 provides quantitative estimates for potential energy, cost, and carbon emission reductions based on common interventions in educational buildings. Calculations are based on

- Annual energy consumption: 180,000 kWh/year for both blocks (from monthly totals in results)
- Electricity tariff: ₹8 per kWh (typical institutional rate)
- CO₂ emission factor: 0.82 kg CO₂ per kWh (Indian grid, 2024)

A deep learning framework is proposed in⁽²⁾ for the energy profiles of various works places in a building and also accounts for the generating sources feeding them. An evolutionary algorithms is presented in⁽³⁾ to build a smart education big data platform to promote the intelligent development of higher education and better assist the establishment of the smart education systems.

Therefore, based on^{(2), (3)} works, this article compared and addressed the Random Forest model achieved high predictive accuracy despite noisy and mixed-use conditions, enabling reliable forecasting and practical diagnosis of inefficiencies such as outdated lighting, prolonged operation of fans and computers beyond required hours, and uneven load distribution across floors and time slots that intensified demand peaks. Based on these insights, the article addressed interventions including optimized scheduling of high-power equipment, replacement of inefficient luminaires, improved utilisation planning for projectors and shared devices, and redistribution of loads to smooth peaks measures that can reduce electricity consumption, operational costs, and carbon footprint while strengthening evidence-based energy planning, budgeting, and sustainability-oriented policy development at institutional scale.

Table 16. Energy Saving Scenarios

Intervention	Estimated Energy Saving	Annual Energy Saved (kWh)	Cost Reduction (₹/year)	CO ₂ Reduction (tons/year)
LED Lighting Retrofit	25% lighting load (10% total)	18,000	₹1,44,000	14.8
AC Scheduling & Thermostat Optimization	15% of AC load (7% total)	12,600	₹1,00,800	10.3
Peak Load Shifting	6% total consumption	10,800	₹86,400	8.9
Occupancy-based Controls	8% non-lab load	8,640	₹69,120	7.1
PC Power Management	10% of PC load (3% total)	5,400	₹43,200	4.4

4 Conclusion

The analysis of electricity utilisation in the B and C Blocks of Methodist College of Engineering and Technology clearly indicates that campus energy demand is strongly influenced by load composition, laboratory usage, and academic scheduling patterns. The study quantitatively establishes that peak-load scenarios increase total daily energy consumption by more than 35-45% compared to moderate academic operation days, primarily due to the simultaneous operation of laboratory equipment such as motors and transformers along with conventional loads. By combining conventional engineering-based load surveys with machine-learning predictions, this study provides a realistic assessment of energy consumption behaviour and anticipated demand across the campus. Statistical feature-importance analysis using the Random Forest algorithm reveals that total connected load contributes approximately 40-50% to monthly energy variation, while the combined influence of lighting and ventilation loads (fans and lamps) accounts for nearly 25-30%. Floor-wise equipment distribution further explains nearly 15-20% of demand variability, highlighting the spatial dimension of institutional energy modelling. Based on these findings, the study recommends the deployment of advanced sub-metering systems to enable improved forecasting, real-time monitoring, and sustainable energy management across the campus.

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References

- 1) Chaer I, Ozarisoy B, Ismail MAE, Salari S, Zhihui Y. Energy efficiency in educational buildings: A systematic review of smart technology integration and occupant behaviour. *Building and Environment*. 2025;280:113132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2025.113132>.
- 2) Dharssini ACV, Raja SC, Karthick T, Venkatesh P. Energy Pattern Classification and Prediction in an Educational Institution using Deep Learning Framework. *Electric Power Components and Systems*. 2022 Jul;50(11–12):615–635. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15325008.2022.2139432>.
- 3) Zheng L, Wang C, Chen X, Song Y, Meng Z, Zhang R. Evolutionary machine learning builds smart education big data platform: Data-driven higher education. *Applied Soft Computing*. 2023;136:110114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2023.110114>.
- 4) Qiu S. Improving Performance of Smart Education Systems by Integrating Machine Learning on Edge Devices and Cloud in Educational Institutions. *Journal of Grid Computing*. 2024 Mar;22(1):41. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10723-024-09755-5>.
- 5) Godasiaei SH, Ejohwomu OA, Zhong H, Booker D. Integrating experimental analysis and machine learning for enhancing energy efficiency and indoor air quality in educational buildings. *Building and Environment*. 2025;276:112874. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2025.112874>.
- 6) Laayati O, Hadraoui HE, Guennoui N, Bouzi M, Chebak A. Smart energy management system: design of a smart grid test bench for educational purposes. *Energies*. 2022;15(7):2702. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15072702>.
- 7) Madabathula CT, et al. Smart green energy management for campus: an integrated machine learning and reinforcement learning model. *Smart Cities*. 2025;8(1):30.
- 8) Shah SFA, et al. The role of machine learning and the internet of things in smart buildings for energy efficiency. *Applied Sciences*. 2022;12(15):7882. <https://doi.org/10.3390/smartcities8010030>.